

ORGANIZATION OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN THE ENTERPRISE

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Annotatsiya: This article describes the skills, rules and perspectives of organizing marketing activities for small business enterprises.

Key words: theory of marketing activity, European society, economic cooperation, National Marketing Association, Market awareness, Spotify, Top marketing ranking.

Introduction. Marketing activity is an activity that consists of organizing and managing the production and sale of goods of the enterprise. The term "marketing activity" was introduced into use in the 60s of the 19th century by McCovern. Marketing as a theoretical concept and a unique phenomenon of commercial activity was first used in the USA at the beginning of the 20th century. High concentration of production and capital, dominance of monopolies in economic sectors, emergence of fierce competition in the international market objectively brought the problem of product sales to the fore. In 1908, the first specialized firm to study marketing problems appeared in the United States. In 1911, a number of large companies of the time opened their first commercial research departments. "Marketing" departments began to be established at companies, which deal with market research, advertising, customer service and other tasks of management. In 1931, the American Marketing Society was formed, and in 1937, the American National Marketing Association was formed. international marketing organizations such as the International Marketing Federation, the European Society for Public Opinion and Marketing and the European Marketing Academy were established. Marketing is one of the modern professions called marketing

Knowing the market (comprehensive study of consumers, knowing their tastes and desires), adapting to the market, influencing the market are the main principles of marketing. Also, a comprehensive study of issues related to the application of

marketing; product range planning; formation of demand and trade promotion activities; sales and distribution; management and control determines the content of marketing activities. Experts outline 9 main functions of marketing: planning and product creation; determining the type and standards of the product; product purchase and its grouping; sale; storage; transport service; financing of marketing activities; gathering information about risks and markets.

Since the 1980s, marketing courses have been taught in economic schools in Uzbekistan. During these years, scientists such as S. Salimov, S. Fylomov, A. Bekmurodov, J. Jalolov, marketing Kasimova, D. Muhitdinov, marketing Nasreddinova, Kh. Raimov conducted scientific research work. In 1986, the first marketing department was established in the "sovplastital" joint venture. Later, joint-stock company "Tashkent Textile Machinery Plant", "V. Marketing departments have also been opened in enterprises such as "Tashkent Aviation Production Association" named after P. Chkalov, joint-stock company "Tashkent Agricultural Machinery".

Methods. At its core, marketing organization is a set of methods, forms and tools for managing the production process with the greatest efficiency. This includes the relationships between departments performing certain functions, assigning responsibilities to certain individuals and departments. The purpose of organizing marketing at an enterprise is to strengthen or change existing positions.

The areas that require organization are:

1. Study, forecasting and market analysis.
2. Assessing the company's internal potential.
3. Defining goals for the future.
4. Development of marketing tactics and strategies.
5. Sales promotion and demand generation.
6. Control.

Almost always, marketing organization is associated with management structure and optimization of marketing activities. This is ensured by monitoring the marketing environment, developing and implementing tactics and strategies that are appropriate to external factors, competently distributing tasks and identifying control mechanisms.

Today, most of a company's relationships with market components are based on marketing principles. The main ones are:

- market research from a scientific and practical point of view;
- study of production and sales opportunities;
- market segmentation;

- flexibility of production and sales policy;
- innovativeness of production;
- planning, etc.

It turns out that marketing in an enterprise is a technological, economic, social and managerial process, the principles of which are:

1. Market monitoring with subsequent analysis of its dynamics and behavior.
2. Constant adaptation to market requirements and consumer needs.
3. Market development in optimal directions.

All these principles help maintain the stability, dynamism and flexibility of the enterprise.

Many researchers agree that there are three basic principles for organizing marketing activities in an enterprise:

1. Achieving the final result of production and sales activities.
2. Goal for long-term results.
3. Tactics and strategies aimed at actively meeting customer requirements.

The first principle means the most effective implementation of the planned volume of goods and services on the market. Therefore, it is important to capture the market share that meets this requirement.

The second principle implies an increased interest in forecasting the situation, as well as developing such goods and services that will bring maximum profit in the market.

The latter type is aimed at the consumer and influencing him to induce a purchase.

Marketing in an enterprise is based on a set of methods, in the form of a system of tools and methods of various types of activities. Therefore, the methodological basis of marketing borrows knowledge from such areas as psychology and sociology. With their help, consumer motivations are analyzed, testing, surveys and other types of research are carried out.

General scientific methods are also used that help to work with information: collect it, process it, systematize it. They help evaluate market behavior, its capabilities, find the most profitable marketing solutions, and optimize marketing activities in general.

Marketing is also inseparable from mathematics, statistics, psychophysiology and other exact sciences, because a marketing organization cannot exist without specific methods, accurate assessment and calculations, and analysis.

The latter is often used to study external and internal resources, study the consumer audience, study both existing goods and those planned for production, organizing sales and turnover, as well as pricing policy.

To achieve its goals and objectives, marketing relies on the following organizational methods:

1. Product orientation method.
2. Customer-oriented method.

Organization of marketing activities can be carried out using various types of structures:

- linear;
- matrix;
- divisional.

The choice of method depends on various factors, and each company has its own. The choice is also affected by goals, objectives and various types of opportunities: personnel, financial or organizational.

Results. Spotify is a service that provides music streaming. It is used by most people around the world. Therefore, let's see what marketing strategy helped the service achieve such success.

At the core of Spotify's marketing strategy is a focus on how Spotify differs from similar platforms. In particular, the service allows the user to easily discover new tracks and filter songs depending on their mood and genre. Spotify's artificial intelligence creates individually selected playlists for each user. The algorithms are so well trained that they often hit the mark. The service gives users a completely new experience when listening to music or podcasts. Therefore, a feature of Spotify is its alternative user interface.

IKEA's marketing strategy is to position itself as a brand that aims to improve lives through everyday little things. IKEA products are highly functional and at the same time accessible to everyone, since the prices are low.

Therefore, the company's goal is not only to sell its products, but also to improve the quality of life of consumers. The basis of IKEA's marketing strategy is to identify the needs of the target audience. Each of us has heard the famous phrase of the brand - "Just Do It". But it's unlikely that you've thought about what's behind this phrase and how it affects consumers' perception of the brand.

Figure 1. Statistics of 1-month main expenses of famous IT companies in the world (approximate)

Nike initially positioned itself as a brand offering sportswear and footwear. However, the company changed its marketing strategy and relied on promotion through values and the formation of a community of people. The bottom line is that consumers felt included and connected. The most famous are the "Just Do It" and "If You Have a Body, You're an Athlete" campaigns that have contributed to Nike's significant success. The company works not only on the quality of the product, but also on the overall impression of the brand. Starbucks designed a logo that is known throughout the world. In addition, the company makes every visitor feel special and tries to create a feeling of home.

In their marketing strategy, Starbucks focused on making the coffee shop a so-called "third place", in addition to home and work. The goal is that people will want to spend their free time at Starbucks. That is why coffee shops have everything you need: Wi-Fi, many sockets, comfortable seats, pleasant music. One of the important points of Starbucks' marketing strategy is the desire to serve customers 24/7. For example, if a person is traveling, shopping or coming home from work, then he

should be able and willing to look into a coffee shop. This allows you to make the product an integral part of life.

Conclusion. In terms of environmental adaptability, the functional structure is able to respond to quantitative fluctuations in demand, but coordination is not sufficient to solve larger problems. Therefore, it is better suited for companies with a homogeneous production program. It should be remembered that there is no ideal marketing organization structure that would be suitable for all conditions. When choosing a structure, the company's goals and environmental conditions should be taken into account.

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